

SAVE JULIA! LOTTERY GAME

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Abstract:

Main method of this lottery game is based on cybersecurity tool called Kim System from Bilbut Security Tools [5]. I designed game this way because it would be relatively easy to integrate game to a computer software in such a way that creating losing and winning scratch-off games could be methodized and, therefore, be compatible with computers.

Game is indeed fun and interesting for players because offers a thematic to keep player engaged and also provider players with new ways of winning such as multiple chances to win with a single bought scratch-off game.

Game is not totally a scratch-off game, even if still an instant game, because it depends on a global result. Furthermore, best to create a digital version of the game is described in these pages.

Please find in the following GitHub repository a sample software of this lottery game ticket generation method: <https://github.com/bilbut/Save-Julia>

I. Introduction

A. Visual Representation of the Scratch-off Game

X	Y	COLOR	GRID	THEME
89	3	Orange	x A a M 5 E	
23	410	Blue	0 z A H	
99	50	Green	7 b 1 C Q F 4	
7	203	Grey	V 2 A P	
320	67	Black	6 G 3 A T A	
217	110	Light Orange	5 A R Y K A	
14	111	Yellow	A 8 J	
107	14	Purple	B s A 9	

RESULT:

AbCY8

INSTRUCTIONS:

INSTRUCTIONS GO HERE

BAR CODE GOES HERE

Picture shows a visual representation of the scratch-off game.

B. Quick Note:

I should mention that game, behind the scenes, can get complex in technical details. However, for players it would be easy to play. Computers would process game easily once there is a system that replicates the methods and steps I am going to describe in these papers.

C. Description:

- A lottery game that offers the best of the jackpot and scratch-off games into a single game, keeping players entertained, willing to win and aware of game news on prizes and other updates.

D. How does this game relate to jackpot games?

- Jackpot games depend on the “winning numbers” chosen. For example, where I live there is a famous jackpot called Powerball. Players are very aware of the exact day and time that winning numbers are randomly chosen.
- However, there is a small difference from traditional jackpot games:
 - o Save Julia! chooses winning “numbers” (results) since day one, and then players have a certain time such as two (2) weeks to try to obtain that result by buying scratch-off games for a certain price.
- There are also advantages from jackpot games:
 - o Since results are given at the beginning of the set period of time such as two (2) weeks, it is not absolutely necessary to choose results randomly, but I do recommend that results are chosen randomly by following the method behind this game (more on this method in the following pages).
 - o Entity offering games to players would have the ability to select or configure:
 - The different prizes.
 - Amount of money for each different prize.
 - Numbers of winners for each given prize.
 - o Game design makes it possible to have statistics of winners in real time, so that the rest of players are aware.

E. How does this game relate to scratch-off game?

- Game is a scratch-off game that is normally bought at retail for instant winning.
- However, results depend on the jackpot.

F. What are the major benefits of this new lottery game?

- Entity offering game has control over prizes, amounts and the limit of winners.
- Motivates players to play because results are given beforehand.
- Players can re-use game for up to five (5) times for a total of six (6) chances of winning with the same scratch-off game (more on this in the following pages).
- Instant winning.

- Method makes it simple, using computers, to create winning and losing scratch-off games.
- Version for a digital game can be created without further design engineering.

G. From where did you get the name? What is its purpose?

- Purpose: Entertainment and adding fun.
- Julia is the name of a woman who is actually a mess. Even mess or not, she must live in this world because every atom of her tells her that she has something to offer to her friends, family, community and rest of humankind. But most of all, she has a rare need to prove things to her herself and to conquer her destiny.
- However, Julia is a good person who is fully surrounded by friends and family members.
- Those family members and friends are the ones who are going to help Julia to get out or “save” her from her own messes that she encounters in the long road of making her dreams a reality.
- Players are Julia’s family members and friends.
- Games winners are the ones who save Julia from the messes, so she can move on.

H. How to integrate this introduction story to the game?

- When results are announced at the beginning of the gaming time cycle, also tell players what is the mess that Julia ran into such as:
 - o Example 1: *Julia needs to go to her new job, which is located in the big city she lives in. However, she did not pay for a GPS feature in her cell phone plan. So, Julia called his friends to see if any of them could give her tips on how to arrive to her job. Who knows? Perhaps one of her friends is close to her and picks her up.*
 - o Example 2: *Her grandparents come to visit her in her apartment, but she has a mess in there. Her grandparents arrive in just thirty (30) minutes, so Julia asks for help to a few of her known neighbors to help her clean up her apartment.*

I. What are my recommendation regarding this story?

- Idea is to follow the analogy to make it funnier for players. Let’s focus on example 1:
 - o Prize with the least amount of money: It is for a friend who tells Julia that her job is next to a blue building.
 - o Prize with the greatest amount of money: It is for a friend who pick her up and takes her to her new job because this friend works in the same place that Julia will work.
- Offer souvenirs to winners of each prize:
 - o For the small prize offer winner, a customized agenda showing pictures of the blue building.
 - o For the big prize offer a small car (toy) and a diploma of best friend at work.
 - o This part of the game is open to the imagination, while the intention behind all this purpose is to offer more entertainment and even loyalty from players to the game.

II. Explanation of the Parts of the Game

A. Theme:

- Theme is where all of the process of arriving to results takes place.
- It could be any picture, but I recommend it to be colorful and beautiful drawings.
 - o Colorful, in this case, comes from the process of method and not related to beauty.
- As now you can imagine, the Color column from the scratch-off game above is related to the theme in a direct way.
- In a digital version of the game, there should be at most one hundred (100) themes for players to choose from. More than that, it would lose the point.

B. Grid:

- Grid dimensions (pixels) and theme dimensions (pixels) should be the same one because we are going to overlap the grid over the theme like this:
 - o Dimensions in this case are: width and length (in pixels)

- Lines can be drawn in any way as long as:
 - o they are closed surfaces (from math concept of area).
 - o there are many closed surfaces.
 - o Closed surfaces do not overlap over each other.
- Each closed surface carries a single letter, number or any other printable symbol (ASCII printable characters).

- Please refer to ASCII Printable Characters [1].
- No open surfaces with symbols are allowed.
- At least 80% of total closed surfaces should have characters inside them.
 - There should be at least one closed surface with the letters from the result.
 - If result is AbCY8:
 - There should be at least one closed surface with letter A (uppercase in this case)
 - At least one closed surface with letter b (lower case in this case).
 - At least one closed surface with letter C (upper case).
 - At least one closed surface with letter Y (upper case).
 - At least one closed surface with number 8.
 - Characters can be repeated amongst closed surfaces without restrictions.
 - **One character per closed surface in the grid. This is important.**
- Closed surfaces can have many forms such as:
 - Circles
 - Squares
 - Rectangles
 - Triangles
 - Trapezoids
 - Ellipses
 - Any other form as long as:
 - There are many closed surfaces
 - Form is a closed surface
 - **Closed surfaces cannot overlap over each other.**
 - Closed surfaces can be continuous to each other or not.
- The idea for the digital version of the game is to have at most one hundred (100) grids ready, and this includes the characters that are to be inside the closed surfaces.
 - More than one hundred (100) grids would not make the point because player would have too many choices to choose from, decreasing player's chances of winning.

C. Coordinates X and Y:

- From now on, and as an example, let's assume that theme's and grid's dimensions (height and width) are 100 pixels by 100 pixels (100px by 100px).
- X and Y stand for coordinates on the theme.
 - Each coordinate represents a specific pixel from the theme.
- A picture is worth more than one thousand (1000) words.

- So, as an example:

Coordinates	Description of position (All are corners)
(0,0)	Upper-left corner
(100, 0)	Upper-right corner
(0, 100)	Bottom-left corner
(100, 100)	Bottom-right corner

Please remember that these dimensions are 100px by 100px (as an example).

- As a last example, where would be located pixel with coordinates (50, 50)?
 - o Answer: In the center of the theme.

D. Color:

- Do you remember when I said that colorful was part of the method?
- Up to now, we have been doing the following:
 - o Select a theme.
 - o Select a grid with same dimensions as the theme.
 - o We overlap the grid over the theme.
 - o Scratch-off game would have already some pre-selected (X, Y) coordinates.
 - o We locate coordinate.
 - o Each coordinate represents a given pixel.
 - o **Each given pixel is represented by the character that is inside the closed surface.**
 - If there is not character in the given closed surface where pixel falls, then no character is added to the result.

- If by any chance a given pixel falls in the exact line (not a closed surface), then no character is added to the result.
- If by any chance a given pixel outside theme's dimensions, then no character is added to the result.
- Each character in the result is added in the order pixel's coordinates are presented (from top to bottom).
- Next step (Color) is knowing the HTML color code of each of those pixels.
- What is the HTML color codes?
 - Using computers, all colors have a numeric representation known as HTML color code [3].
 - This numeric representation is almost always in the hexadecimal numeric system, but for better understanding of the method, I am converting hexadecimal values into the decimal numeric system [2].
- Computers do this easily and quickly.
- Players will not even know that computer is doing all of these calculations and, of course, players do not need to do any of these calculations. For players, it is going to be very easy to play and win (more on this in the following pages).

E. Why do I add the color feature?

- Main purpose of this feature: *The purpose of this feature is increasing the entity offering the game's chances of winning. With this, players' chances of winning decrease. (Please refer to the Odds+ Factor below)*
- Second purpose of this feature: Scratch-off game is going to be outside of a computer, and with it, outside the principal and active system of a computer that says, for example:
 - "Scratch off game is a falsification because pixel's HTML color code on the given (X, Y) coordinate does not coincide with original design."
 - What I mean is that the color feature is a security measure in cases of falsification because it would be very difficult to have the exact HTML color code for a given pixel due to that forger does not have access to a digital copy of the original theme.
 - Please use different themes for scratch-off games and digital version of the game.
 - The possibility of falsification is that an exact copy of the scratch-off game is made. In that case:
 - No two (2) or more equal scratch-off games are to be made (entity offering the game level).
 - Add a bar code that is unique for each scratch-off game (entity offering the game).
 - For example, in case of pixel (89, 3), from the visual representation of a scratch-off game at the beginning of this document, it has the orange color assigned.
 - Using a winning scratch-off game as guide:
 - How does forger know what exact color represents the given pixel? Forger can attempt to approximate color but there always will be certain difference.

F. Odds+ Factor:

- Instead of having a coordinate in the form:
 - (X, Y)

- Let's add the following to form what is known as an ordered triple.
 - o (X, Y, HTML Color Code)
- For example, pixel on coordinates (89, 3), from the visual representation of a scratch-off game at the beginning of this document, has an orange color assigned to it.
- Ordered triple = (89, 3, HTML Color Code of Orange).
- What would happen if theme's HTML color code of pixel (89, 3) is blue?
 - o Answer: No character is added to results.
- Note: I am referring to colors using their names, but it is actually using their respective HTML color code number.

G. How to make a scratch-off game? (Step by Step Guide):

- 1) Select a theme.
- 2) Select a grid with same dimensions as the theme. Grid should have the corresponding characters inside.
- 3) We overlap the grid over the theme.
- 4) We select (X, Y) coordinates as well as the HTML color code of the pixel on that coordinate.
- 5) We annotate the coordinate and HTML color code on the respective columns. This step includes the Odds+ Factor.
 - a. When annotating the HTML color code, please do not use the exact decimal or hexadecimal number. Instead, translate the HTML color code to a visual representation of the color.
- 6) We locate the closed surface where pixel falls.
- 7) (if any) We take the character that the closed surface has.
- 8) We add the character to the result from left to right.
- 9) Repeat steps 4-8 for seven (7) more times for a total of eight (8) possible characters in the result.

III. How to Offer and Win the Game

A. How does it works?

Please note that when players scratch-off the game, there would not be an instant result until the bar code is scanned to verify if player won. There is no manual way of knowing without the "Online System."

When I refer to the "Online System," I mean all the system used from verifying scratch-off game (device + online server) to actually verify game to see if it is a winner to update statistics to create prizes to create scratch-off games for players to play.

B. Quick and Important Details?

- Each scratch-off game should have a unique bar code on it.
 - o Online system used to verify if a scratch-off game is a winner should have at least the following two (2) data when a bar code is sent for verification:
 - Year and Quarter Number in the form: YEARQ#.
 - For example, 2020Q1
 - Result of the given scratch-off game.
- Like I said at the beginning, each time cycle if going to be of two (2) weeks.

- One (1) Quarter consists of 3 months, and a total of four (4) quarters in a year.
- Three (3) months are twelve (12) weeks.
- 12/2 is equal six (6) times.

C. How to create prizes?

- Entity offering the game creates prizes, amounts of money for each prize and the number of winners to be assigned to each prize.
- How to create a prize technically?
 - o Think about a winning scratch-off game.
 - Follow the above guide: How to make a scratch-off game? (Step by Step Guide):
 - o Create a winning scratch-off game and take result.
 - o Result can be, for example, AbCY8.
 - o Then hash that result [4].
 - Hash is going to be used by the Online System to compare the player's game result with the actual results for the given prizes.
 - Player's game result must also be hashed using the same hash function in order to be compared to Online System's hash(es).
 - o Repeat this process for the number of prizes that want to be created.
 - o Online System should have assigned an amount for each prize and the number of winners for each winner.
- When a scratch-off game is scanned to verify if it is a winner, then Online System compares result and year plus quarter assigned to the specific player's game.
- Modern technology makes it relatively simple to update the Online System regarding the number of winners and can do much more such as:
 - o Send email to retailer.
 - o Get current location of player.

When user exchanges winning scratch-off game for the amount of the prize, then take manual security steps.

- One of these steps would be to reproduce original game and compare to the one of player.
 - o Online System should save a visual representation of each game created.

D. Some Additional Rules:

- In order to increase odds of winning for players, let's do as follows:
 - o Let's make each game valid for the rest of the given quarter.
 - o This means each game can be used up to six (6) times.
 - o Game would can be used, during a given quarter, once every two (2) weeks.
- Human psychology says that people would tend to not wait until two (2) weeks passes.
- This will increase the number of scratch-off games bought as well as the number of people playing the game because it gives some appearance of "I can win this..."
- The number of odds is actually controlled by the entity offering the game because:
 - o They control the number of winning scratch-off games.

- Because each bar code has assigned the respective scratch-off game's result, then it could be possible to know beforehand the number of winners for each prize, even if the number is zero.
- With the above, entity offering the game can control (limit) the number of winners as well as the amount for each prize.

E. What player are required to do?

- 1) Buy scratch-off game.
- 2) Scratch off.
- 3) Scan bar code to see if they won.
- 4) That's it!

F. Tips for players:

- Results are up to eight (8) characters.
- It is almost certain that entity offering the game is going to set results of winning games to at least five (5) characters long.
- It is recommended that player do not keep games with results with less than five (5) characters long because even if players play up to six (6) times, they would not win at any of those times.

IV. Online Version of the Game

A. Differences with the Scratch-Off Game:

- Result is not shown: This increases the house's chances of winning because player does not know the length of the result (number of characters in the result) and has to take risk of playing without knowing if player is a potential winner (five (5) or more characters in result).
- Bar code is not necessary.
- However, new and different instructions are needed in order to keep player informed on how to play. These instructions can be interactive and show them one at a time.
 - For example:
 - "Click on Select Grid and select a grid."
 - "Select a Theme."
 - "Click on Generate Values or enter them manually."
 - Etc.
- Player does not have the option to re-use game.
 - One (1) game is equal to one (1) play.
- **There is no jackpot: Prizes and results are pre-defined.**

However, game is still an instant winning game.

B. New Characteristics:

- Story should be on screen with option to skip Julia's mess.
- Total amount of earned money should be on screen.
- Option to generate the following values **or enter them manually**:
 - Coordinate X
 - Coordinate Y
 - Color (more on this in the following pages)
- There should a pop-up window in the following cases:
 - Select Grid: window with at most one hundred (100) pre-defined grids.
 - Select Theme: window with at most one hundred (100) pre-defined themes.

- Prize A, Prize B and Prize C: windows describing respective prizes' amounts and also describing how player could help Julia get out of mess.
- My Prizes: window showing the number of prizes player has won up to now.
 - Perhaps there could be a trajectory estimate) of player's possible results for the following three (3) months based on the past three (3) months of play.
- Play: This option is to verify if player is a winner based on all the current options and choices (configuration such as chosen coordinates X and Y, color, selected grid and theme) on screen.
 - Perhaps it would be a good idea to only allow one (1) play per given configuration.
- Automatic Play: Automatically set a configuration and play.

C. Visual Representation of Digital Version of Game:

- Please refer to the following visual representation of the digital version of the game.

D. Color:

- When player is selecting color, there should visual representations of colors:

- Table with multiple columns and rows showing colors as in filled circles.
 - Each circle inside each table's cell.
- However, the main difference when compared to the scratch-off game is that those circles are not going to represent (to be equivalent) to a specific HTML color code as in the scratch-off game.
- **Each color in the circles is going to represent a *range* of HTML color codes.**
 - For example (numbers are less than one hundred (100) because theme, in the example, is 100px by 100px):
 - These are not real HTML color numbers.

Color	Pixel's Coordinates	Pixel's Color	Range (From color player selected)	Does it count towards result?
Red	(20, 1)	300	From 200 to 330	Yes
Blue	(17, 54)	878	From 100 to 120	No
Green	(50, 67)	234	From 50 to 230	No
Yellow	(8, 37)	98	From 90 to 100	Yes

E. Suggestion for Real World Functioning:

- I would suggest to follow the spectrum of visible light.
- For example, green color:
 - Give a range or, if necessary, multiple ranges in order to cover all the possible variations of green color. Please remember that ranges are based on the HTML color codes.
- Take a look:

- However, "green color" is too simple.
- It should be light green, green and dark green colors.
 - This means that those three colors are not one (1) but three (3).
- Do the same with the rest of colors (if applicable).
- For example:

- o These are not real HTML color numbers.

Light Green	Green	Dark Green
[0, 50]	[51, 99]	[100, 120]

This is basically the lottery game!

REFERENCES

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